

ANALYSIS OF DAMAGE INITIATION
IN COMPOSITE MATERIALS

Xue Yuan-de
Department of Engineering Mechanics,
Tongji University,
Si Ping Road 1239,
Shanghai, China

ABSTRACT

Three major damage modes, i.e. transverse cracks, edge delamination and fiber breaks, in composite materials are analyzed to furtherly understand how they are caused. The stresses at the fiber/matrix interface are numerically calculated using sub-structure technique of Finite Element Method (FEM), which shows that the interface debonding is formed firstly and then follows the matrix cracking. The normal interlaminar stresses in $[0/90]_S$ and $[0/90/0/90]_S$ laminates are also calculated using FEM. We conclude that the normal stresses at the interlamina between 0 degree and 90 degree plies in both laminates are larger than that at the symmetrical mid-plane between 90 degree plies. The longitudinal stresses in those fibres near the broken fibres are analyzed. As the branch cracks, caused by the transverse and shear stresses, appear and the damage area extends, the longitudinal stress mentioned above is getting smaller and finally approaches to a steady value.

INITIATION OF TRANSVERSE CRACKS

Initiation of transverse cracks is caused by the fact that the fibers having higher elastic-modulus are embedded into the matrix having lower one, which results in the overstresses at fiber-matrix interface and then the interface debonding appears when the transverse plies are loaded by tensile stresses perpendicular to the fibres. The following is the transverse cracks in matrix of those plies. [1]

So a mechanical model of composites under transverse tension is set up to calculate the stresses in fibres, resin and interface. Assuming that the arrangement of fibres is regular and not at random, for instance,

a square arrangement, so that we can take a "Representative Volume Element" from a layer of the transverse plies to analyze. In order that the damage process can be calculated and described, the sub-structure technique of Finite Element Method is used. Regarding fibre as a "main-structure" and matrix as a "sub-structure", we think that the two sets of node-points at interface in fibre and matrix are combined with each other before damage occurs and then they are dis-combined while the interface debonding is propagating. It's necessary to determine the boundary forces acted each other between this element and its neighbour one. Because of its difficulty, a boundary constraint condition is given, i.e., assuming that those node-points lying in a same section of boundary before deformation remain lying in another parallel section after deformation to keep the continuity of displacement of two neighbour elements. In this model, fibres are regarded as elastic and resin matrix as inelastic according to a given nonlinear stress-strain curve.

The computational results show that, even though the external loads or displacement are tensile, there exist all three kinds of stresses: tension, compression and shear stresses at fibre-matrix interface, and their values are larger than those in matrix. The distribution curves of these stresses are shown in Fig.1. We can conclude that, at $\theta=90^\circ$, the normal stress σ_r is tensile and reaches its maximum value, but at $\theta=0^\circ$, σ_r is compressive. The values of shear stress $\tau_{r\theta}$ in the region of $\theta=30^\circ-60^\circ$ are much larger than those in other region. Considering the difference between the behaviours of different types of resin which can result in interface debonding or matrix yielding, we also calculate the maximum tension stress σ_{max} and the effective stress σ_i .

Fig.1. The stress distribution at the fibre/matrix interface in the transverse plies.

For the most of epoxy resin, the tension behavior appears to be brittle and the factor that controls the failure is the maximum tensile stress σ_{\max} , so that the interface debonding in transverse plies occurs firstly at $\theta=90^\circ$, then it propagates to the other region of interface and stops up to the compressive stress appearing at interface. And the displacement of the previous structure are shown in Fig.2. After the occurrence of interface debonding, the matrix is bearing more parts of the load, because matrix can't transfer a large amount of load to fibre. At last, the transverse cracks in matrix are formed.

Fig.2. The opening displacement at the interface in the transverse plies in existence of the interface debonding.

Fig.3. The inelastic stress distribution in matrix of the transverse plies.

For other types of resin, in which yielding is easy to occur, the factor that controls the failure is the effective stress σ_1 or the maximum shear stress τ_{\max} . Yielding occurs firstly at the interface in the region

of 30° - 60° , then it gradually propagates to the most region of resin, as shown in Fig.3. Because the tensile stress σ_r at interface is still increasing non-linearly related to external loads or displacements, at last the interface debonding also occurs.

INITIATION OF EDGE DELAMINATION

The interlaminar normal and shear stresses at the free-edge in cross-ply composite laminates are caused by the difference between the Poisson's ratio ν_{xy} of zero degree ply and that one of 90 degree ply. Generally, the free-edge stress field is three dimensional and the FEM is used to calculate the interlaminar stresses in a $[0/90]_8$ multiply laminate.

It's very interesting that at the free-edge the interlaminar normal stress σ_z reaches its maximum value near the interface between zero degree and 90 degree plies, where z equals $h/4$. And if the meshes of the finite elements get finer, the interlaminar normal stress σ_z in the middle plane where z equals zero approaches to a constant value which equals that one obtained by Pipes and Pagano, but the interlaminar normal stress σ_z near the interfaces between zero degree and 90 degree plies gets greater and doesn't approach to a constant value. In order to furtherly clarify this problem, an eight-ply laminate $[0/90/0/90]_8$ is analyzed using three dimensional FEM. The numerical result shows that at the free-edge, the interlaminar normal stress σ_z also reaches its greater value near the interfaces between zero degree and 90 degree plies and it changes from tension to compression at the interfaces as shown in Fig.5. We think that the results obtained above are very useful to understand how the edge delamination forms.

Fig.4. Distribution of the interlaminar normal stress σ_z in $[0/90]_8$ laminates.

Fig.5. Distribution of the interlaminar normal stress σ_z in $[0/90/0/90]_s$ laminates.

INITIATION OF FIBRE BREAKS

It's well known that, though fibre has very high strength, the tension strength of brittle fibres has very large scatter. When the composite is loaded under the longitudinal tensile stress, individual fibre may be broken firstly, which results in the overstress in its neighbour fibres. But the behaviour of the matrix in the neighbourhood of the broken fibre and the ability of the matrix to transfer load around the fracture site are very dependent on the properties of the fibre/matrix interface.

A new mechanical model, in which a damage area consisting of multi-branch cracks caused by the interface debonding is inserted in front of the broken fibres, has been suggested by us [2]. The analytical-finite element method is used to obtain the analytical solution in the global outside area and the displacements obtained on outside/inner boundary are employed as the prescribed displacement boundary condition for the solution of inner damage area. Then the finite element method is also used for the solution in the inner area.

We conclude that, when the branch crack appears the longitudinal tension overstress σ_y in the first unbroken fibre neighbouring to the broken fibres turns to be a finite value and keeps a relatively uniform value along the y direction. As the length and number of the branch cracks increase and the damage area of material between the branch cracks extends, this overstress σ_y is getting smaller and finally approaches to a steady value. From this computational results, if the interface strength is suitable for forming the interface debonding in the neighbourhood of the broken fibres, it's of benefit to the composites to reach its

higher longitudinal tension strength, which has testified by the experimental result obtained from C/Al composites. [3]

Fig.6. Relaxation of the longitudinal tension overstress σ_y in the first unbroken fibre caused by the different length b of the branch cracks.

CONCLUSION

Based on the analysis mentioned above, we conclude that the fibre /matrix interface and the interlamina between two plies are of weakness in FRP-Composites, where the damage always occurs firstly. But in general, the local failures such as interface debonding, delamination, or matrix cracking and yielding do not cause the fatal failure of a multilaminate and they often result in the stress redistribution in fibres of composites. And the most important factor, controlling the last failure of entire laminate, is the fibre breakage.

REFERENCES

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